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Simulation-Based Thermal Assessment and Heating Strategy Evaluation for the A320 Cargo Compartment

Simulationsbasierte thermische Bewertung
und Heizstrategien des Frachtraums eines A320

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the thermal behaviour of the forward cargo compartment of an Airbus A320 and evaluates the feasibility of using the avionics system (AVS) exhaust air as an internal heating source. Maintaining adequate cargo temperatures remains a challenge in narrow-body aircraft, particularly during cruise conditions, where the fuselage is exposed to very low external temperatures. To address this, a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model was developed to analyse airflow, temperature distribution, and heat transfer mechanisms within the cargo bay.

A three-dimensional geometry based on the A320 forward cargo compartment was created and meshed in ANSYS Fluent using poly-hexcore and inflation-layer strategies to resolve near-wall gradients and internal recirculation structures. Boundary conditions representing realistic environmental control system (ECS) behaviour were applied, using steady-state simulations were conducted. A zonal modeling approach was employed to validate the numerical results against experimental temperature measurements from previous studies. The comparison demonstrated a close match in most regions, confirming the suitability of the model for evaluating cargo heating concepts.

The study focuses on one heating strategy, the direct injection of AVS exhaust air below the cargo volume. This approach theoretically provides the highest heat-recovery potential but requires system-level assessment due to safety and integration constraints. Simulation results show that introducing AVS exhaust air can significantly increase cargo air and wall temperatures and reduce cold spots near the fuselage skin. Temperature fields, wall heat fluxes, and airflow patterns were analysed to quantify the thermal improvement and assess the distribution uniformity within the compartment.

The outcomes of this work offer valuable insights into the effectiveness and limitations of AVS waste-heat utilisation for cargo heating. The validated CFD framework provides a foundation for future studies, including alternative injection concepts, design optimisation, and integration into complete ECS architectures.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
A/C	Aircraft
A320	Airbus A320 aircraft / aircraft family
AVS	Avionics System (exhaust air)
BC	Boundary Condition
BoI	Body of Influence (mesh refinement zone)
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CHT	Conjugate Heat Transfer
ECS	Environmental Control System
FTF	Flight Test Facility (Fraunhofer IBP)
HTC	Heat-Transfer Coefficient
HX	Heat Exchanger
IBP	Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics
LES	Large-Eddy Simulation
OFV	Outflow Valve
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes
SST	Shear Stress Transport (turbulence model)
STELLA	German aviation research programme (project name)
TAS	True Air Speed
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (if applicable in diagrams)

List of Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
— Thermodynamic Quantities —		
T	Temperature	K, °C
T_{skin}	Fuselage skin temperature	K
T_{cargo}	Cargo air temperature	K
$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,A}}$	Volume-avg. cargo temperature (Case A)	K
$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,B}}$	Volume-avg. cargo temperature (Case B)	K
T_{exp}	Experimental mean temperature	K, °C
T_{CFD}	CFD-predicted temperature	K, °C
ΔT	Absolute temperature error ($T_{\text{CFD}} - T_{\text{exp}}$)	K
— Fluid Dynamics —		
U	Velocity magnitude	m/s
p	Static pressure	Pa
ρ	Density	kg/m ³
μ	Dynamic viscosity	Pa·s
Re	Reynolds number	—
— Heat Transfer —		
q	Heat flux	W/m ²
k	Thermal conductivity	W/mK
h	Heat-transfer coefficient	W/m ² K
c_p	Specific heat capacity	J/(kg·K)
— Flow Rates & Geometry —		
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	kg/s
\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate	m ³ /s
d	Diameter (e.g., vent-hole diameter)	m
A	Area (cross-section / opening)	m ²
V	Volume	m ³
D	Hydraulic diameter / pipe diameter	m

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

The thermal management of aircraft interior compartments is a central function of the Environmental Control System (ECS), which is responsible for ensuring comfortable and safe temperature conditions for passengers, crew, and cargo [3, 4]. While the cabin is actively conditioned through a well-regulated air supply, the cargo compartments of commercial aircraft, particularly in narrow-body configurations such as the Airbus A320, often exhibit larger temperature variations and are more sensitive to environmental fluctuations [5, 6]. This is primarily due to their location along the lower fuselage, where the aircraft skin is exposed to extremely low outside-air temperatures that can drop below $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during cruise [3, 7, 8].

Unlike the passenger cabin, cargo bays receive only limited conditioned airflow and typically rely on indirect heating mechanisms [8, 9]. In the A320, the forward cargo compartment is partially influenced by warm air circulating below the cabin floor; however, heat transfer is constrained by structural insulation, ventilation layout, and compartment geometry. As a result, cold spots frequently develop near the fuselage skin, and maintaining cargo temperatures within acceptable limits, especially for temperature-sensitive goods such as pharmaceuticals or electronics, remains a design and operational challenge [6].

To address these restrictions, researchers and aircraft manufacturers have explored alternative heating concepts that utilise existing heat sources within the aircraft [8, 9]. One promising candidate is the waste heat generated by the avionics system (AVS). Avionics equipment produces a continuous thermal load during operation, and its exhaust air is typically routed overboard [9]. Redirecting this warm exhaust air toward the cargo compartment offers the potential to enhance thermal conditions without increasing energy consumption or adding significant system complexity.

Accurate assessment of such heating strategies requires a detailed understanding of the air-flow and heat transfer behaviour inside the cargo compartment. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has therefore become a vital tool for analysing aerothermal environments in enclosed aircraft spaces [10, 8, 11]. CFD simulations allow for the investigation of ventilation patterns, wall heat fluxes, recirculation zones, and temperature distributions under representative operating conditions. When combined with a zonal modelling approach anchored in experimental measurements, CFD provides a robust framework for evaluating design modifications and predicting

thermal performance with high spatial resolution [12, 9].

In this context, the present study focuses on developing and validating a CFD model of the A320 forward cargo compartment and applying it to analyse the feasibility and thermal effectiveness of an AVS exhaust-air heating concept. The background presented here establishes the broader importance of cargo thermal management and the role of simulation tools in advancing ECS design and optimisation.

1.2 Motivation

Improving the thermal environment of aircraft cargo compartments requires a heating strategy that is both effective and compatible with existing environmental control system (ECS) architectures. Among the potential solutions for enhancing cargo temperatures, the use of waste heat from the avionics system (AVS) has received growing interest. AVS equipment produces a steady thermal load, and its exhaust air represents an accessible and energetically favourable heat source. Several conceptual strategies have been proposed for redirecting this heat toward the cargo compartment, each with distinct implications for system integration, safety, and overall feasibility.

Three principal options are under consideration:

Option 1 (fig 1.1a) – Direct supply of AVS exhaust air into the cargo hold. This approach offers the highest theoretical efficiency, as the AVS exhaust air is delivered directly into the cargo volume without intermediate losses. However, it requires a substantial redesign of the cargo ventilation system, including major modifications to the cargo exhaust fan, to resolve the flow mismatch between the AVS exhaust and existing ventilation rates. Additionally, this option raises safety concerns, as a malfunction or smoke emission from the AVS bay could lead to contaminated air entering the cargo compartment. For these reasons, Option 1 is considered operationally unsuitable and has been disregarded for further study.

Option 2 (fig 1.1b) – Blowing AVS exhaust air below the cargo floor. In this concept, AVS exhaust air is routed into the subfloor region beneath the cargo compartment. This allows warm air to directly heat the cargo floor structure, thereby addressing one of the known cold spots in the compartment: the cargo floor and the adjacent cold bilge area. Importantly, this option does not require any changes to the existing cargo ventilation configuration, making it both technically feasible and operationally nonintrusive. Because it combines high heating potential with minimal system modification, Option 2 represents a promising and realistic solution.

Option 3 (fig 1.1c) – Air-to-air heat exchanger from AVS exhaust to cargo inlet air. This alternative uses an air-to-air heat exchanger to transfer thermal energy from AVS exhaust air to the conditioned air supplied to the cargo inlet. It requires only minor changes to the ECS ducting but necessitates additional hardware, increasing system weight, complexity, and maintenance demands. The feasibility of this solution is currently linked to the sizing and performance of the heat exchanger, which remains under investigation.

Comparison of the Three Options

Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1 Comparison of the three investigated heating strategies for utilising AVS exhaust heat in the A320 forward cargo compartment.

Among the three options, Option 2 presents the best balance between thermal benefit, integration effort, and system safety. For this reason, the present thesis focuses exclusively on analysing the thermal performance of Option 2 using a validated CFD model of the A320 forward cargo compartment. This targeted investigation aims to determine whether subfloor AVS exhaust air injection can effectively mitigate cold zones and elevate cargo temperatures under realistic operational conditions, thereby supporting future ECS design decisions.

1.3 Objectives

The overarching objective of this thesis is to evaluate the thermal effectiveness of using an avionics system (AVS) exhaust air as a heating source for the Airbus A320 forward cargo compartment, with particular focus on the subfloor injection strategy (Option 2). To achieve this, a computational framework is developed to simulate the airflow, temperature distribution, and heat transfer processes under representative operating conditions.

The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

1. Develop a three-dimensional CFD model of the A320 forward cargo compartment, including the cargo volume, floor structures, and the subfloor region, using a geometry and mesh configuration suitable for accurate thermal analysis.
2. Establish realistic boundary conditions based on available aircraft data, including AVS exhaust air properties, ambient conditions, cargo ventilation characteristics, and relevant wall thermal behaviour.
3. Validate the CFD model using a zonal comparison against experimental temperature measurements from previous studies to ensure that the simulation accurately represents the thermal behaviour of the cargo environment.

4. Implement and analyse the AVS subfloor heating concept (Option 2) by introducing AVS exhaust air beneath the cargo floor and evaluating its influence on internal temperature fields, wall heating, and reduction of known cold spots.
5. Assess the thermal performance and limitations of Option 2 by examining airflow patterns, temperature distributions, and heat-flux characteristics inside the cargo compartment.
6. Provide insights and recommendations regarding the feasibility of AVS waste-heat utilisation for cargo heating and identify key factors for future ECS design optimisation or extension to alternative heating concepts.

These objectives collectively aim to determine whether AVS subfloor air injection can serve as a viable and effective method for improving cargo thermal conditions without significant system redesign.

Chapter 2

Background

Commercial aircraft cargo compartments are part of the lower fuselage and form a thermally sensitive environment that must comply with safety, structural, and environmental requirements. this chapter provides a comprehensive introduction to the structural layout, material composition, thermal environment, and airflow mechanisms of typical aircraft cargo compartments, with a focus on the Airbus A320 family.

2.1 Fuselage Structural Architecture

The fuselage of a commercial aircraft is designed using a **semi-monocoque structure**, [13, 14] which consists of:

- an outer aluminium skin that carries aerodynamic loads,
- vertical *frames* that maintain the fuselage shape,
- longitudinal *stringers* that provide stiffness,
- floor beams that support cabin and cargo floors.

The cargo compartment is located in the **lower lobe** of the fuselage. This region lies between the aircraft skin and the passenger cabin floor [15].The cargo compartment is located in the lower lobe of the fuselage. The lower deck is dedicated to passenger luggage as well as additional freight transportation Figure 2.1 illustrates a Finite element model of typical structural cut of the A320 fuselage, showing frames, stringers, floor beams, and insulation layers.

2.2 Cargo Compartment Layout

The forward cargo compartment of the A320 consists of three main regions:

1. **Cargo air volume** – the space where baggage and freight are stored.
2. **Cargo floor structure** – a load-bearing assembly of aluminium beams and floor panels.
3. **Bilge region** – the space beneath the cargo floor and above the outer fuselage skin.

Figure 2.1: The under-floor structure of cabin (luggage and cargo floor are hidden) [1]

2.2.1 Floor and sidewall construction

The cargo floor is typically an aluminium sandwich panel comprising:

- 50 mm thick aluminium floor panels (structural),
- supported by longitudinal floor beams [13],
- with openings that allow air exchange between bilge and cargo.

The vertical walls forming the cargo lining are made from lightweight 10 mm honeycomb composite panels [16], selected for their:

- low mass,
- fire resistance,
- thermal insulation properties,
- ease of cleaning and certification.

Behind these walls lies a space containing insulation blankets made from foam-glass, mineral wool, or similar materials [16]. These insulation layers reduce heat loss to the environment but are significantly limited during cruise due to very low external temperatures.

2.2.2 Bilge Region

The bilge is the compartment located between the cargo floor and the aircraft skin. It contains:

- hydraulic lines,

Figure 2.2: Finite element model of fuselage section with luggage [1]

- structural elements,
- wiring bundles,
- the outflow valve (OFV) ducting,
- water drainage channels.

Because the outer skin can reach -50°C at altitude [3, 17], the bilge is one of the coldest areas of the aircraft [17, 18], and heat transfer from this region strongly influences the cargo thermal environment.

2.3 Environmental Control System (ECS) Airflow

The cabin and cargo compartments of transport aircraft are supplied by the Environmental Control System (ECS), which conditions bleed air or compressor air to maintain pressurisation, ventilation, and thermal comfort [3, 17]. In typical narrow-body aircraft configurations, the ECS primarily serves the passenger cabin, delivering a mixture of fresh and recirculated air, while only a limited portion of conditioned air is routed to non-cabin zones such as the cargo compartments. Air is extracted from the pressurised fuselage through the outflow valve, which regulates cabin pressure and indirectly governs the global ventilation flow path.

2.3.1 Cargo Ventilation System

In narrow-body aircraft such as the Airbus A320 family, cargo ventilation and heating are not part of the baseline ECS architecture but are implemented as optional systems. When installed,

cargo ventilation relies on dedicated ducting, isolation valves, and extraction devices to provide controlled airflow through the cargo compartment, typically exhausting toward the lower fuselage and outflow valve region. Compared to the passenger cabin, the airflow rates supplied to the cargo hold are significantly lower, and the ventilation system is primarily designed to meet safety and certification requirements rather than to ensure thermal comfort [19].

As a consequence of the limited ventilation rates, cargo compartment temperatures are governed primarily by conductive heat transfer through the fuselage structure, the thermal performance of insulation layers, and heat exchange with the passenger cabin through the cargo floor. These mechanisms dominate the thermal balance of the cargo volume, particularly during long-duration cruise conditions.

2.4 Thermal Challenges in Cargo Compartments

Cargo compartments are subject to demanding thermal conditions during flight. At cruise altitude, the external fuselage skin can reach very low temperatures, resulting in strong conductive heat losses through the aircraft structure. Due to the comparatively weak ventilation, the cargo compartment has a limited capacity to compensate for these losses through convective heat input. In addition, the extensive use of aluminium structural elements provides efficient conduction paths that further promote heat extraction from the cargo air volume.

These factors promote pronounced thermal stratification within the cargo compartment, with warmer air accumulating near the ceiling and colder air settling toward the lower regions. The bilge area, located beneath the cargo floor and in close proximity to the cold fuselage skin, typically represents the coldest zone. As a result, local cold spots commonly develop near the lower sidewalls, at the cargo floor edges, within the triangular side volumes, and in the bilge region. Without dedicated heating measures, cargo air temperatures may fall below freezing, posing a risk to temperature-sensitive goods [17, 20].

2.5 Existing Heating Approaches

To mitigate low cargo temperatures, several heating and thermal management concepts have been implemented or proposed within the aviation industry [18, 21]. One approach consists of increasing the ECS airflow supplied to the cargo compartment; while effective, this strategy can negatively affect cabin air distribution and increase overall energy consumption. Localized electric heating elements have been applied in some wide-body aircraft, but they introduce additional mass and certification complexity. Recirculation fans can enhance mixing within the cargo volume, but do not provide a direct heat source. Alternatively, heat exchangers have been proposed to transfer thermal energy from other aircraft systems into the cargo airflow.

Despite their potential benefits, these solutions are often associated with increased system mass, higher energy demand, certification challenges, and significant modifications to the existing ECS architecture. These limitations motivate the investigation of alternative concepts that can enhance cargo thermal conditions while minimising system-level penalties.

2.6 AVS Waste Heat as a Heating Source

The avionics system (AVS) produces continuous waste heat during operation [18, 22]. Traditionally, AVS exhaust air is discharged overboard. Reusing this heat for cargo heating is attractive because:

- it is available throughout the flight,
- it represents “free” energy that would otherwise be wasted,
- it can reach temperatures of 25 °C to 30 °C [22],
- AVS airflow rates are comparable to cargo ventilation demand [18].

Three concepts were evaluated at the conceptual design level:

1. **Option 1: direct injection into the cargo compartment** (high efficiency, high contamination, and redesign risk).
2. **Option 2: subfloor injection into the bilge** (no ventilation redesign, strong heating benefit).
3. **Option 3: AVS-to-cargo heat exchanger** (moderate redesign, additional mass and cost).

Option 2 was selected as the most feasible and is analysed in detail in this thesis.

2.7 Summary

This chapter provided the structural and thermal background required to understand the cargo-compartment environment, the limitations of existing heating systems, and the motivations for investigating AVS waste-heat reuse. The following chapters build on this foundation to present the modelling approach, validation results, and performance assessment of the subfloor AVS heating concept.

Chapter 3

State of the Art

This chapter reviews the theoretical, experimental, and numerical foundations relevant to the thermal behaviour of aircraft fuselages, with particular focus on cargo compartments under cold-soak cruise conditions. The objective is to situate the present thesis within the current scientific landscape, identify the remaining knowledge gaps, and define the motivation for the modelling and validation strategy adopted in later chapters. To this end, the chapter synthesises research on Environmental Control Systems (ECS), fuselage heat transfer, cabin and cargo airflow behaviour, and advanced thermal–fluid simulation methods, supported where applicable by full-scale fuselage experimental data.

3.1 Introduction and Research Question

Transport-aircraft fuselages represent highly coupled thermal–fluid systems [23, 5] in which ECS supply air, structural heat conduction, and buoyancy-driven or forced convection interact to determine the temperature distribution in the cabin, bilge, and cargo compartments. While cabin thermal comfort has been the subject of extensive investigation [5], the thermal behaviour of forward cargo holds under cold-soak conditions remains less comprehensively documented. Very low fuselage-skin temperatures [3], limited ventilation, and the absence of internal heat sources often produce strong vertical gradients, pronounced bilge cooling, and spatially non-uniform thermal fields.

A further gap exists in the systematic evaluation of alternative heating strategies for cargo compartments. One promising, yet largely unexplored, concept involves re-routing warm avionics-system (AVS) exhaust air through a perforated pipe installed below the cargo floor to provide additional heating without major architectural modifications.

Motivated by these open questions, the present thesis addresses the following research question:

To what extent can warm AVS exhaust air injected below the cargo floor improve the temperature distribution and mitigate low-temperature regions in the A320 forward cargo compartment, relative to the baseline ECS configuration, when analysed using experimentally validated three-dimensional steady RANS conjugate heat-transfer (CHT) simulation?

Answering this question requires an integrated review of fuselage thermal physics, ECS and ventilation system modelling, numerical aerothermal simulation approaches, and available full-scale fuselage experimental datasets. The subsequent sections therefore outline the theoretical framework, summarise global fuselage and ECS models, review cabin and cargo airflow studies, discuss additional insights from cargo-fire and special-conditions research, and synthesise the outcomes to define the methodological approach adopted in this thesis.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

3.2.1 Thermal Environment of Transport-Aircraft Fuselages

The internal thermal environment of a pressurised aircraft fuselage is shaped by the interaction of three tightly coupled subsystems:

1. **Environmental Control System (ECS):** Outside air—supplied either as bleed-air or via electrically driven packs—is conditioned, mixed with recirculated cabin air, and distributed to the cabin, cockpit, and in some configurations to the cargo hold. Exhaust air leaves the fuselage through outflow valves and leakage paths.
2. **Fuselage structure and insulation:** The multi-layer thermal resistance formed by aluminium or composite skins, frames, stringers, floor beams, and insulation blankets governs the conductive heat flux between the cold exterior and internal cabin, bilge, and cargo volumes.
3. **Internal heat sources and sinks:** Occupants, galleys, avionics, lighting, and cargo generate sensible heat, while in special configurations warm AVS or electronics-exhaust air may be routed through underfloor regions for thermal management.

At cruise altitude, exterior temperatures typically range from -20 °C to -55 °C [3] depending on altitude and atmospheric conditions. The resulting temperature gradients drive conduction through structural elements—particularly thermal bridges such as frames and floor beams—and induce vertical stratification in cabin and cargo compartments. Full-scale fuselage experiments confirm that such stratification remains significant even with well-mixed ECS supply air [24, 5].

From a heat-transfer perspective, the fuselage can be idealised as a set of coupled fluid and solid regions connected by:

- convection between air and structural surfaces,
- conduction within fuselage skins, insulation layers, and floor panels,
- radiation between interior surfaces (typically secondary for cruise conditions),
- mass and enthalpy exchange via ECS-driven or buoyancy-driven ventilation flows.

Natural convection plays a dominant role due to density differences between warm upper regions and cold regions near the fuselage skin and bilge. Accurate near-wall turbulence modelling is therefore essential for high-fidelity numerical simulation.

3.2.2 ECS Function and Simulation Approaches

Modern ECS architectures including conventional bleed-air systems, electrically driven packs, and hybrid concepts have been the subject of extensive modelling and simulation. Celikel et al. present a numerical framework for analysing electrical ECS behaviour [25] and its interaction with the thermal environment of the fuselage. Pathak and Norrefeldt expand this perspective by evaluating hybrid ECS configurations incorporating vapour-cycle systems [26], demonstrating the importance of integrated thermal and systems-level modelling. Although these studies do not focus specifically on cargo heating, they highlight the need for coupled fluid–thermal models that capture ECS control, airflow distribution, and structural conduction.

3.2.3 Heat and Mass Transport in Aircraft Interiors

Foundational work by Wörner provides detailed insight into heat and mass transport processes in aircraft interiors [27]. Key findings include:

- pronounced vertical stratification driven by buoyancy,
- strong influence of structural conduction on local air temperatures,
- interaction of supply-air jets with curved fuselage geometry,
- significant thermal coupling between cabin, floor, bilge, and cargo air volumes.

These characteristics underline the necessity of using conjugate heat-transfer (CHT) modelling to simultaneously resolve fluid motion and structural heat conduction. For cargo holds—where limited ventilation, cold exterior conditions, and structural conduction strongly interact—CHT approaches are especially important for predicting temperature gradients and assessing novel heating concepts such as AVS-based underfloor air injection.

3.3 Thermal–Fluid Fuselage Modelling

A wide range of modelling approaches exists for analysing the coupled thermal–fluid behaviour of aircraft fuselages. These approaches differ significantly in fidelity, computational cost, and their ability to resolve localised phenomena such as cold bilge zones, steep vertical gradients, and the thermal impact of underfloor heating concepts. The following subsections summarise the main categories found in the literature and highlight their relevance for the present study.

Comparison table 3.1 of modelling approaches for fuselage thermal–fluid analysis.

3.3.1 0D/1D System-Level Models

Lumped-parameter and network-based models represent each compartment as a single or small set of thermal nodes with averaged properties. Mass and energy balances are solved using ordinary differential equations, typically implemented in equation-based environments such as Modelica.

Oehler developed one of the first comprehensive global thermal–fluid fuselage models, coupling ECS behaviour with cabin, cargo, and structural thermal nodes [23]. The model reproduces spatially averaged temperature levels and global thermal responses under a variety of ECS operating conditions. Similar approaches have been used for ECS control development (e.g. Gangaraju, Pollok [12]), where computational efficiency and robustness are prioritised over spatial resolution.

Despite their usefulness for system design and control studies, 0D/1D models cannot resolve:

- cold bilge regions and localised temperature minima,
- convection patterns induced by ECS or AVS jets,
- conduction through specific structural members (frames, floor beams),
- the thermal impact of localised heat sources or perforated ducts.

These limitations make them unsuitable for evaluating detailed cargo heating concepts or underfloor flow patterns.

3.3.2 Zonal and Multi-Node Modelling

Zonal approaches divide the cabin or cargo compartment into several interconnected volumes with simplified heat- and mass-transfer correlations. They offer moderate fidelity and can capture overall stratification trends and global temperature gradients at significantly lower computational cost than full CFD [28].

However, they remain unable to predict:

- detailed flow structures in the bilge and underfloor regions,
- the effect of structural thermal bridges,
- jet penetration from supply slots or AVS exhausts,
- local cold spots at the cargo floor.

Thus, while zonal models improve upon lumped-node representations, they still do not provide sufficient resolution for analysing localised heating concepts.

3.3.3 Three-Dimensional CFD with Conjugate Heat Transfer

High-fidelity three-dimensional CFD, combined with conjugate heat transfer (CHT), resolves both the internal flow field and solid-region conduction. RANS or LES solvers allow the prediction of:

- buoyancy-driven stratification and natural-convection cells,
- conduction through skins, beams, and floor structures,
- cold downdraughts near the fuselage sidewall,
- interaction of supply or AVS jets with curved fuselage geometry,

- thermal behaviour of highly confined bilge volumes.

While 3D CHT has been widely applied in cabin comfort studies and, separately, in cargo-fire scenarios (e.g. fire detection, smoke transport, suppression efficiency), validated simulations of cargo compartments under cold-soak conditions remain scarce. Pathak et al [29]. demonstrate the integration of simulation with full-scale cargo tests for fire-protection systems, confirming the feasibility of high-fidelity modelling but focusing on fire behaviour rather than thermal management.

For evaluating the thermal effect of underfloor AVS injection especially the localised temperature rise near vent holes, the interaction with bilge stratification, and the mitigation of cold-soak regions—3D CHT is the only approach capable of providing the required spatial resolution.

3.3.4 Implications for the Present Thesis

The literature consistently shows that:

1. Global fuselage and ECS system models can reproduce averaged temperatures and support ECS control studies, but treat cargo and bilge regions too coarsely for local thermal analysis.
2. Zonal and multi-node models provide intermediate fidelity but still lack the ability to resolve detailed convection and structural conduction paths.
3. Only 3D CFD with CHT can capture the localised physical phenomena relevant for assessing AVS-based cargo heating concepts under cold-soak conditions.

For these reasons, the present thesis adopts a 3D CHT framework, constrained by system-level insights and validated against experimental data from the Fraunhofer IBP Flight Test Facility (FTF).

3.4 Experimental Foundations: Fraunhofer IBP Flight Test Facility (FTF)

3.4.1 Fraunhofer IBP Flight Test Facility (FTF)

The Fraunhofer IBP Flight Test Facility (FTF) is a full-scale single-aisle fuselage mock-up designed for controlled aerothermal experiments under representative ECS and external conditions. The facility includes realistic cabin, floor, insulation, and cargo structures. Within the STELLA project [30, 31] a comprehensive measurement concept was developed, providing high-resolution and spatially distributed data through:

- vertical temperature ladders in the cabin, cargo, and bilge,
- surface-temperature sensors on fuselage linings, floor panels, and insulation layers,
- dense sensor networks in the triangular side volumes and bilge region,
- humidity, velocity, and selected surface heat-flux sensors.

This setup enables systematic investigation of thermal stratification, recirculation zones, humidity distribution, and heat transfer through the fuselage structure. Previous work, such as Wörner [24], demonstrated the strong thermal coupling between cabin, underfloor, and cargo regions, reinforcing the need for conjugate (air–structure) modelling rather than purely internal flow simulations.

3.4.2 Relevance for the Present Thesis

The dataset provided by Fraunhofer IBP includes detailed measurements of:

- skin, floor, cargo-air, and bilge-air temperatures,
- vertical temperature arrays at several lateral positions,
- controlled ECS and AVS boundary conditions.

These measurements enable:

- multi-point validation of the numerical model for both baseline and AVS-pipe cases,
- assessment of flow-induced mixing, thermal gradients, and stratification,
- evaluation of cold-soak behaviour and structural coupling effects,
- verification of predicted air and surface temperature fields against experimental data.

Overall, the FTF dataset forms a robust experimental foundation that significantly enhances the credibility and accuracy of the fuselage CFD model developed in this thesis.

3.5 Cargo Compartment Ventilation and Heating Concepts

3.5.1 Conventional Cargo Ventilation

Narrow-body aircraft such as the A320 provide only minimal ventilation to the forward cargo compartment [23]. Air typically enters through a small underfloor supply slot and exits via sidewall vents or leakage paths into the bilge before being routed toward the outflow valve. This ventilation architecture results in:

- weak forced convection and limited mixing,
- high dependency on structural conduction for heating,
- strong vertical stratification under cruise conditions,
- the bilge consistently being the coldest region of the fuselage.

Studies by Oehler and Wörner show that cold bilge temperatures strongly influence cargo-air temperatures during cruise [23]. These findings underline the need for improved heating strategies to mitigate cold-soak effects in the lower cargo compartment.

3.5.2 Alternative Heating Concepts

Various heating approaches have been proposed, including resistive heating mats, structural heating elements, underfloor heat exchangers, and modified ECS ducting. While technically feasible, these solutions increase mass, system complexity, and certification effort, or incur significant energy penalties.

Despite these investigations, there is **no published work** evaluating the reuse of warm avionics-system (AVS) exhaust air for cargo heating. Likewise, there are **no studies** analysing perforated underfloor pipes designed to deliver AVS air into the bilge region as a passive heating mechanism. This gap motivates the novel configuration explored in the present thesis.

3.5.3 Cargo-Compartment CFD and Ventilation Studies

Compared with the extensive literature on passenger-cabin environments, only a relatively small number of studies address cargo compartments. Most published CFD work focuses on regulatory topics such as fire detection, smoke transport, or extinguishing-agent distribution. These simulations commonly use RANS (k - ε or SST) turbulence models with simplified boundary conditions and typically omit detailed fuselage conduction. Representative examples from the fire-protection community [29] emphasise:

- flow paths during smoke spread,
- inert-gas distribution during suppression,
- detection times and sensor placement.

Thermal fields and cold-soak conditions are generally not examined.

Within the STELLA and IBP FTF campaigns, CFD has been used to interpret cabin measurements and design experimental scenarios. Some studies couple global Modelica simulations with CFD sub-models; however, published cargo-specific CFD for cold-soak thermal behaviour remains extremely limited.

Overall, the open literature contains only a few examples of fully coupled, geometry-resolved 3D conjugate-heat-transfer (CHT) simulations of the cargo–bilge–floor system under realistic ECS boundary conditions and validated against detailed measurements. Addressing this gap is one of the core contributions of the present thesis.

3.6 Cargo Fire and Special-Condition Compartments

3.6.1 Environmentally Friendly Fire-Protection Studies

Pathak and co-workers developed and validated a simulation tool for environmentally friendly cargo fire-protection systems [32], combining reduced-order CFD correlations with Modelica-based system modelling [23]. Their validation used extensive data from fire tests in a full-scale cargo-compartment test rig. Although the focus is on fire suppression rather than thermal management or cold-soak behaviour, the study provides:

- detailed descriptions of cargo-ventilation layouts and flow paths,

- insights into instrumentation concepts and measurement uncertainties,
- evidence that system-level tools can be validated for complex cargo-compartment phenomena when supported by full-scale experiments.

3.6.2 Measurement Concepts and Gradient Evaluation

The STELLA measurement-concept documentation [30] describes the spatial arrangement of temperature sensors in the FTF, including detailed ladders in the cabin, cargo, bilge, and triangular side volumes. These measurements are specifically designed to capture vertical gradients near the cabin floor, cargo floor, and bilge—quantities of direct relevance to the present thesis.

The IBP experimental campaign used as validation input in this study follows this concept, providing high-quality, position-resolved data suitable for assessing a high-resolution 3D CHT model of the cargo compartment.

3.7 Synthesis of Research Gaps

The reviewed literature establishes a solid foundation in global fuselage modelling, ECS analysis, cabin airflow studies, and cargo-compartment fire simulations. Full-scale fuselage test facilities further provide high-quality experimental data for validation. However, several key gaps remain unresolved:

1. **Cold-soak cargo behaviour remains underexplored.** Most prior work focuses on cabin comfort or cargo-fire scenarios; continuous cold-soak cruise conditions with extremely

low skin temperatures and minimal ventilation receive limited attention.

2. **Lack of high-fidelity 3D CHT models resolving the cargo–bilge–floor geometry.** Existing system-level and zonal models treat cargo and bilge regions as single volumes and do not capture local conduction paths, cold bilge pockets, triangular side volumes, or detailed convection structures.
3. **Absence of validated CFD for cargo heating.** While CFD has been widely used for smoke, fire, and cabin studies, there are almost no published examples of validated, geometry-resolved 3D conjugate-heat-transfer simulations for cargo temperature prediction under cold-soak conditions.
4. **No published work on AVS exhaust as a passive cargo-heating source.** AVS waste heat is normally vented overboard. Its reuse via a perforated underfloor pipe for bilge heating has not been investigated in the open literature.
5. **Limited quantitative data on vertical thermal gradients in cargo compartments.** Strong cargo-floor and bilge gradients are known to exist, but few studies document their behaviour or evaluate how they respond to alternative heating concepts.
6. **Need for combined experimental–CFD validation frameworks.** Although fire-protection projects and cabin studies show that combined modelling and full-scale testing is feasible, no published work applies such a methodology to cargo heating under cold-soak conditions.

Together, these gaps highlight the need for a detailed, experimentally validated 3D CHT investigation of alternative heating mechanisms in the A320 forward cargo compartment.

3.8 Positioning of the Present Study

To address these gaps, the present thesis:

- develops a high-fidelity three-dimensional steady RANS CHT model of the A320 forward cargo hold, resolving cargo air, bilge air, triangular side volumes, fuselage skin, structural elements, and the cargo floor;
- applies realistic boundary conditions informed by full-scale IBP cold-soak measurements and prior ECS modelling work;
- models an innovative perforated AVS exhaust pipe installed below the cargo floor to explore its potential as a passive heating mechanism;
- validates both the baseline ECS configuration and the AVS-assisted configuration against independent experimental temperature data from the Flight Test Facility;
- analyses temperature fields, vertical gradients, flow structures, and heat-transfer pathways to quantify the thermal impact of AVS injection.

This study therefore provides:

1. one of the first validated high-resolution CHT simulations of a cargo compartment under realistic cold-soak cruise conditions,
2. the first published quantitative assessment of AVS exhaust air as a passive cargo-heating strategy, and
3. insights that can be integrated into system-level ECS and fuselage modelling frameworks, strengthening the link between detailed CFD and global aircraft thermal analysis.

Table 3.1: Comparison of modelling approaches for fuselage thermal–fluid analysis

Modelling level	Description	Strengths	Limitations	Typical applications
0D/1D system models	Lumped thermal nodes solved in Modelica/Simscape or similar tools.	Very fast; suitable for ECS design and control; reproduces global behaviour.	No spatial resolution; cannot resolve cargo/bilge gradients or conduction pathways.	ECS control design, parametric sweeps, system-level studies.
Zonal / multi-node models	Few interconnected zones capturing coarse vertical stratification.	Moderate fidelity; efficient for early design and sensitivity studies.	Unable to resolve local flows or detailed floor/bilge physics.	Reduced-order thermal modelling, fast architectural trade studies.
3D CFD (air only)	Full 3D airflow modelling without explicit solid conduction.	Captures flow structures, jets, recirculation and mixing.	Incomplete heat-transfer representation; no structural conduction through walls/floor.	Cabin ventilation studies, smoke and contaminant transport.
3D CFD with CHT	Full RANS/LES airflow coupled with heat conduction in solids.	High fidelity; resolves bilge, insulation, floor beams and structural heat paths; required for heating concepts.	High computational cost; requires detailed geometry and careful validation.	Cargo cold-soak analysis, AVS heating concept evaluation, insulation design.
CFD + experimental validation	Numerical models calibrated and validated against full-scale measurements.	Ensures reliability and predictive capability; supports extrapolation to new conditions.	Requires complex, controlled test campaigns and detailed instrumentation.	Novel concept validation, high-accuracy design studies, certification support.

Chapter 4

Research Methodology

This chapter presents the methodological framework used to investigate the thermal effect of injecting warm AVS exhaust air beneath the A320 forward cargo compartment. The methodology is designed to ensure that the numerical model is (i) physically representative of the real aircraft fuselage, (ii) consistent with established approaches in the literature, and (iii) validated against high-quality experimental measurements from the Fraunhofer IBP Fuselage Test Facility (FTF). The overall workflow combines detailed geometry representation, experimentally derived boundary conditions, advanced meshing strategies, conjugate heat-transfer (CHT) simulation, and structured post-processing and validation.

Research design and methodological workflow of the study figure 4.1.

4.1 Research Strategy and Overall Workflow

Based on the gaps identified in Chapter 3, the methodology follows a structured five-step approach:

1. **Define a representative geometry.** Reconstruct a cross-section of the A320 forward cargo compartment, including cargo air, bilge, floor, honeycomb walls, insulation layers, fuselage skin [33, 34], and the AVS pipe (Case B only).
2. **Apply physically grounded boundary conditions.** Use measured temperatures from IBP experiments [30] (skin, floor, cabin), real ECS flow rates, and recorded AVS exhaust parameters to impose realistic thermal and fluid boundary conditions.
3. **Generate a high-quality mesh using Poly-Hexcore topology.** Ensure sufficient resolution in the bilge, pipe, and floor regions while maintaining computational feasibility (500k- 800K cells).
4. **Perform 3D steady RANS CHT simulations [35] for two cases:**
 - Case A – baseline cargo ventilation only,
 - Case B – AVS-assisted heating using a perforated pipe.

Figure 4.2: Center section of single aisle with ECS ducting [2]

5. **Validate the model and analyse thermal performance.** Compare CFD data with IBP experimental measurements at multiple validation points and evaluate the temperature distribution, velocity field, and thermal gradients.

4.2 Link to Research Questions and Literature

The chosen methodology directly addresses the research questions formulated in Chapter 3. Specifically:

- **CHT modelling** is required because prior literature (Oehler, Wörner) shows strong coupling between air and structure, especially in the bilge and floor regions.
- **Experimental boundary conditions** from IBP ensure the model is grounded in real measured fuselage thermal behaviour rather than purely theoretical values.
- **CFD validation** responds to the lack of published studies comparing cargo thermal behaviour under both baseline and heating configurations using full-scale measurement.
- **Two-case comparison** allows a controlled evaluation of the heating concept by isolating the effect of the AVS warm-air pipe.

Thus, the methodology is a direct continuation of the identified gap: existing literature lacks a validated numerical study of AVS exhaust air used for cargo heating.

4.3 Geometry Modelling Method

4.3.1 Case A: Baseline Cargo Geometry

The baseline geometry represents a forward cargo compartment configuration consistent with a narrow-body aircraft layout. The model includes the cargo air volume, adjacent side cavities, and

the bilge region extending to the fuselage skin. Structural components such as the cargo floor, cargo walls, and surrounding insulation layers are incorporated using simplified but thermally representative solid domains. The upper boundary corresponds to the passenger-floor interface, enabling heat transfer between cabin and cargo zones.

The geometry is constructed to be fully consistent with the experimental measurement locations, ensuring that subsequent numerical results can be directly compared with available validation data.

4.3.2 Case B: AVS Heating Concept Geometry

Case B is derived directly from the baseline geometry and extends it by incorporating an active ventilation and heating system. This system is modelled as a perforated duct located beneath the cargo floor, introducing distributed air jets into the cargo volume. The perforations are oriented to promote effective jet interaction and mixing within the compartment, following established concepts for perforated duct ventilation.

Apart from the addition of the ventilation pipe, all other geometric features are kept identical to the baseline configuration. This approach enables an isolated assessment of the impact of the AVS heating concept through direct comparison between the two cases.

4.4 Boundary Conditions and Experimental Inputs

All boundary conditions are defined based on experimental inputs obtained from controlled cargo-compartment tests. This ensures consistency between numerical simulations and physical measurements and allows the computational model to replicate the tested operating conditions.

4.4.1 Thermal Boundary Conditions

Thermal boundary conditions are prescribed to represent the dominant heat-transfer paths in the cargo compartment. The fuselage skin temperature is imposed to reflect cold-soak conditions representative of cruise operation. The passenger-floor interface is treated as a fixed-temperature boundary derived from cabin measurements. Multi-layer wall and floor structures are modelled using effective thermal representations, allowing conduction through structural and insulation layers to be captured without resolving internal material details.

4.4.2 Fluid Boundary Conditions

The airflow boundary conditions are specified to reproduce the experimental ventilation scenarios for each case. In the baseline configuration, conditioned air is supplied around the cargo compartment and discharged through the bilge outlet. In the AVS configuration, the baseline ventilation is supplemented by an additional warm-air supply introduced through the perforated duct system.

The outlet treatment remains unchanged between cases to maintain consistency. This boundary-condition strategy ensures that the differences in predicted flow and thermal fields primarily arise from the ventilation concept, rather than from changes in external constraints.

Figure 4.3: Half of the Geometry (Case B)

Figure 4.3 shows the ECS and AVS inlet (Blue arrows) and outlet from the bilge (Red arrows) on the geometry of Case B

4.5 Mesh Strategy and Quality

The computational mesh is generated using a hybrid poly-hexcore approach to balance numerical accuracy and computational efficiency. Hexcore elements are employed in the central cargo air volume to provide stable, low-diffusion convection modelling, while polyhedral and tetrahedral elements are used in transition regions surrounding curved surfaces and the AVS duct geometry.

Local mesh refinement is applied through body-of-influence regions in areas where strong velocity and thermal gradients or jet interactions are expected, including ventilation openings, the bilge region, the fuselage skin, and the cargo floor. Near-wall refinement with inflation layers is incorporated to adequately resolve boundary-layer temperature and velocity gradients, and smooth cell-size transitions are maintained to minimise numerical diffusion and enhance solver robustness.

Mesh quality is evaluated using standard geometric criteria, and the final resolution is selected to remain compatible with available computational resources while providing sufficient accuracy for conjugate heat-transfer analysis.[36]

Figure 4.4: Meshing for the middle of the full Geometry

Figure 4.4 illustrates the resulting poly-hexcore mesh topology for the full computational geometry.

4.6 Numerical Modelling and Solver Considerations

The flow and thermal fields are solved using a steady-state, incompressible Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) formulation with the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model, selected for its robustness in internal flows with adverse pressure gradients and strong coupling between momentum and heat transfer.

A coupled pressure–velocity solver and second-order spatial discretisation are employed to enhance numerical stability and reduce diffusion, while conjugate heat transfer is enabled to ensure consistent treatment of conductive and convective heat transport across solid–fluid interfaces. The combination of a poly-hexcore mesh with local body-of-influence refinement and the chosen turbulence model provides an effective balance between computational cost and predictive accuracy.

Convergence behaviour is influenced by steep thermal gradients at solid boundaries, slow stabilisation of recirculating bilge flow structures, and strong thermal coupling, resulting in a relatively high iteration demand.

Convergence is assessed using both residual reduction and physically relevant monitoring quantities, including domain-averaged air temperatures and selected wall temperatures, ensuring that the final steady-state solutions are physically consistent and suitable for subsequent analysis of the AVS heating strategy.

4.7 Validation Procedure

The numerical results are validated against experimental temperature measurements obtained from IBP test campaigns. Validation locations are distributed across key regions of the cargo compartment, including the cargo air volume, side cavities, bilge region, fuselage skin, and cargo floor. This distribution allows both global and local thermal behaviour to be assessed.

For each measurement location, the corresponding CFD temperature value is extracted at the sensor position. Validation is performed by computing absolute and relative temperature deviations between numerical predictions and experimental data. This procedure is applied independently to both Case A and Case B to ensure that the predictive capability of the model is assessed consistently across different ventilation configurations.

4.8 Data Extraction and Analysis

Post-processing focuses on extracting flow and thermal quantities that are relevant to cargo thermal performance and ventilation effectiveness. Temperature fields are analysed using planar slices and three-dimensional visualisations to capture spatial distributions and stratification effects. Velocity vectors and streamlines are evaluated to identify dominant flow paths and mixing mechanisms.

Quantitative analysis includes the evaluation of vertical temperature gradients at selected cross-sections, as well as the computation of averaged and local temperatures within defined cargo zones. Comparative assessment between Case A and Case B is performed using metrics related to minimum cargo temperature, thermal stratification, bilge temperature behaviour, airflow mixing, and overall temperature uniformity.

4.9 Assumptions and Limitations

The modelling methodology is based on a set of assumptions that define the scope of the study and limit the direct applicability of the results. These assumptions are consistent with common practice in aircraft cargo-compartment CFD analyses but should be considered when interpreting the findings.

4.9.1 Geometric Assumptions

The computational domain is limited to the forward cargo compartment, and interactions with adjacent compartments or the cabin are only represented through boundary conditions at the passenger-floor interface. Detailed structural elements such as brackets, wiring, stiffeners, and auxiliary systems are omitted to reduce geometric complexity, with their thermal influence accounted for through effective material representations. Cargo loading, baggage distribution, and moisture effects are not included in the present model.

4.9.2 Boundary-Condition Assumptions

Thermal boundary conditions are prescribed based on laboratory measurements and are assumed to remain constant throughout the simulations. The cabin-floor interface is treated as a fixed-temperature boundary rather than being dynamically coupled to cabin airflow. For the AVS configuration, exhaust-air properties are assumed steady and spatially uniform at the inlet, neglecting potential temporal or spatial variations.

4.9.3 Numerical Assumptions

All simulations are performed under steady-state conditions, and transient effects associated with flight phases or prolonged cold-soak scenarios are not considered. Turbulence is modelled using a RANS approach, which may not capture all small-scale unsteady mixing phenomena. Radiative heat transfer is neglected, as conduction and convection are expected to dominate under the investigated operating conditions. Mesh resolution is constrained by available computational resources, which limits the smallest resolvable flow structures.

4.9.4 Validation Limitations

Experimental validation is limited to discrete temperature measurement locations, and full-field experimental temperature or velocity data are not available. As a result, validation of flow structures is restricted to qualitative comparisons. Only a single side of AVS heating concept is analysed, and alternative configurations are excluded due to feasibility and system-integration constraints. Furthermore, system-level aspects such as pressure losses, duct optimisation, and full aircraft ECS coupling are beyond the scope of this study.

Overall Impact

Despite these limitations, the adopted modelling approach aligns with established aircraft-industry CFD practices and is supported by the reviewed literature. The combination of experimentally derived boundary conditions, discrete validation data, and detailed conjugate heat-transfer modelling provides a physically meaningful basis for evaluating the feasibility of subfloor AVS heating and assessing the potential of the selected heating concept to improve cargo thermal conditions under representative operating scenarios.

Figure 4.1: Research design and methodological workflow of the study.

Chapter 5

Geometry and CFD Model Setup

This chapter describes the numerical model of the A320 forward cargo compartment, including the geometry, mesh generation, material modelling, boundary conditions, and solver settings. The configuration is first defined for the validated baseline without AVS pipe (Case A) and then extended to the AVS-based heating configuration (Case B). Unless otherwise stated, the physical models and solver settings are identical in both cases.

(a) Overview of the poly-hexcore mesh used in Case B

(b) Case B: longitudinal section showing pipe and underfloor region.

Figure 5.1: Hexcore cells dominate the interior, while polyhedral cells capture curvature and boundary-layer variations along fuselage walls and the bilge.

5.1 Computational Geometry

The numerical model represents the lower part of an Airbus A320 fuselage, focusing on the forward cargo compartment and the underlying bilge region. Only the lower half of the fuselage cross-section is included, since the thermal interaction with the passenger cabin is introduced via prescribed boundary conditions at the passenger floor rather than by explicitly modelling the cabin air volume.

5.1.1 Fuselage cross-section

The outer fuselage contour is approximated by a circular arc with a radius of 2.2114 m (dimension R8 in the CAD sketch), which corresponds to the dominant curvature of the lower half of the

Figure 5.2: Single Aisle Cross Section [2]

A320 fuselage [34]. The internal cargo compartment is idealised as an almost rectangular volume embedded inside this arc. The main geometric dimensions are:

- Clear width of the cargo compartment at floor level: 2.84 m.
- Total internal width between the side walls below the passenger floor level: 4.059 m.
- Vertical distance between passenger floor and cargo floor: 0.3024 m.

An illustrative dimension of the CFD geometry is shown in Figure 5.3.

The simplified geometry captures the main features governing the thermal behaviour: the curved fuselage skin, the nearly flat cargo floor, and the bilge volume below the floor where the cold outside temperature is imposed.

5.1.2 Axial extent and domain reduction

In the axial direction, the forward cargo compartment has a physical length of approximately 2.8 m, which is fully retained in the model. To limit the mesh size while preserving the dominant flow and heat transfer mechanisms, only one lateral half of the fuselage is represented. A symmetry plane is placed along the longitudinal centreline, resulting in an effective modelled width equal to the fuselage radius, 2.2114 m.

This reduction significantly decreases the computational cost while still capturing the relevant three-dimensional effects in the vertical and axial directions. The remaining axial boundaries are treated as periodic-like sections with appropriate flow and thermal boundary conditions.

Figure 5.3: 2D of the lower part of Airbus A320 with Dimension

5.1.3 Solid and fluid regions

The geometry consists of three primary domains, later complemented by the AVS warm-air supply duct in Case B:

1. **Cargo air volume (fluid).** The enclosed air above the cargo floor represents the usable cargo compartment. This region is treated as a compressible ideal gas and forms the main evaluation space for temperature and airflow behaviour.
2. **Cargo walls and cargo floor (solid).** The cargo walls are modelled as a 10 mm thick honeycomb panel, representing the lightweight sandwich construction used in real aircraft cargo linings.

The cargo floor is represented with an effective structural height of 50 mm, corresponding to the stiffened aluminium floor panel made of thin sheets and vertical ribs. Although this floor is not a solid slab in reality, the equivalent thickness reproduces the correct overall thermal resistance of the assembly.

3. **Bilge air region (fluid).** The space between the cargo floor and the outer fuselage skin forms the bilge. This air region is directly influenced by the external aircraft skin, which is subjected to the low outside-air temperature.

The passenger-floor boundary above the cargo compartment is not explicitly modelled as a solid body; instead, its thermal influence is imposed via a prescribed temperature and a layered representation (aluminium plus foam-glass insulation).

The external triangle and side-wall regions exposed to the ambient environment are assigned a composite structure consisting of 5 mm aluminium followed by 50 mm foam-glass insulation. The outer boundary is subjected to the outside-air temperature used in the Fraunhofer IBP full-scale experiment, in which the fuselage skin was conditioned to represent typical A320 cruise conditions.

In Case B, an additional fluid region representing the AVS warm-air duct is introduced beneath the cargo floor. The duct is assigned PVC walls and is used to deliver warm AVS exhaust air into the bilge in accordance with the selected heating concept (Option 2).

Figure 5.4: 3D Full lower part of Airbus A320

5.2 Mesh Strategy and Grid Generation

The mesh generation process is critical, as the thermal behaviour of the cargo compartment is strongly influenced by wall heat transfer, near-wall temperature gradients, and recirculating flow structures. Capturing these effects with sufficient accuracy requires a localised mesh-refinement strategy while still maintaining an overall element count compatible with the available computational resources. (Mesh strategy 4.5)

5.2.1 Local refinement using Bodies of Influence

The large temperature difference between the external environment (259.75 K) and the cargo air (288.05 K) in case A leads to steep thermal gradients near solid walls. Resolving heat transfer across the aluminium cargo floor, honeycomb walls, insulation layers, and bilge region requires fine near-wall resolution.

A uniform global refinement would have resulted in more than five million cells for the full-width model. Even with the half-width geometry, a uniformly refined mesh easily exceeded one million elements, leading to high memory consumption and long solution times. To overcome this limitation, *Body of Influence* (BoI) regions were introduced around:

- the cargo floor (high thermal conductivity, key heat-transfer path),
- the bilge and fuselage-skin vicinity (cold external boundary),
- the AVS warm-air duct (high-velocity and high-temperature gradients),
- the lower side walls and insulation layers (thermal bottlenecks).

The BoI technique enables targeted refinement only where needed, with coarser cells in regions of lower sensitivity. This reduced the total cell count to approximately 5×10^5 – 8×10^5 elements, making the model computationally feasible.

Figure 5.5: Cross-section mesh refinement Case A.

Figure 5.5 Overview of the poly-hexcore mesh used in Case A. Hexcore cells dominate the interior, while polyhedral cells capture curvature and boundary-layer variations along the geometry.

Case A: Baseline (without AVS pipe)

For the baseline configuration (without AVS pipe) The computational grid consists of an unstructured poly/mixed mesh generated in ANSYS Meshing. The global mesh statistics are listed in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Global mesh statistics for Case A.

Quantity	Value
Total cells	559,865
Total faces	2,534,796
Total nodes	1,543,448

Mesh quality indicators for all zones are summarised in Table 5.2

Table 5.2: Mesh quality statistics for Case A.

Zone	Cell type	Min orthogonal quality	Max aspect ratio
airplane	Mixed	0.0505	289.95
inside_cargo	Mixed	0.3644	7.36
cargo_wall	Polyhedral	0.2023	27.75

(a) Case A: cell aspect-ratio distribution.

(b) Case A: orthogonal quality histogram.

The majority of cells exhibit an orthogonal quality above 0.85, which is suitable for second-order spatial discretisation.

Case B: AVS exhaust duct

In Case B, the geometry is extended by a cylindrical AVS pipe with an inner diameter of 0.125 m, routed below the cargo floor in the bilge region and aligned with the modelled fuselage segment. The pipe axis is located centrally in the spanwise direction, and the pipe wall is modelled as a solid PVC body to enable conjugate heat transfer.

The mesh is regenerated to include the additional fluid and solid regions, while retaining the poly-hexcore strategy and BoI refinement. Overall statistics are:

Table 5.3: Overall mesh size – Case B (with AVS pipe).

Quantity	Value
Cells	715,969
Faces	3,448,674
Nodes	2,195,245

Mesh quality per region is:

Table 5.4: Mesh quality per region – Case B.

Zone name	Type	Min orthogonal quality	Max aspect ratio
airplane	Mixed cell	0.1125	18.88
inside_cargo	Mixed cell	0.3700	6.64
cargo_wall	Poly cell	0.2047	18.10

(a) Case A: cell aspect-ratio distribution.

(b) Case B: cell aspect-ratio distribution.

All regions satisfy the usual quality requirements for steady RANS heat-transfer simulations (orthogonal quality predominantly above 0.2 and aspect ratio well within solver limits), and no special treatment (non-conformal interfaces, non-orthogonal correctors) is required.

5.3 Material Modelling and Cell Zones

The thermal behaviour of the forward cargo compartment is governed by the material composition of the surrounding structure and by the boundary conditions representing aircraft operation. The major structural elements (cargo walls, cargo floor, insulation layers, fuselage skin, passenger floor and, in Case B, the AVS pipe wall) are represented by materials consistent with typical A320 construction and the Fraunhofer IBP mock-up.

5.3.1 Qualitative structural representation

- **Cargo walls.** Vertical and sidewall panels are modelled as a 10 mm honeycomb composite, typical for aircraft cargo linings. In the CFD model, the honeycomb is treated as a homogeneous solid with effective thermal conductivity based on manufacturer data.
- **Cargo floor.** The floor separating the cargo air from the bilge is represented with an equivalent structural height of 50 mm. The real floor consists of thin aluminium sheets and stiffening ribs; the equivalent thickness reproduces the correct overall thermal resistance.
- **triangle and sidewall insulation.** The outer fuselage region is represented by a two-layer system: 5 mm aluminium (inner skin) and 50 mm foam-glass insulation, reproducing the thermal resistance of typical insulation blankets.
- **Passenger floor.** The passenger-floor surface is treated as a boundary with a layered structure (aluminium plus foam-glass insulation) and a prescribed temperature representing the conditioned cabin above.
- **AVS pipe wall (Case B only).** The AVS exhaust pipe wall is modelled as a PVC solid body to allow conjugate heat transfer between the hot AVS air and the bilge region.

Together, these definitions capture the dominant heat-transfer paths between the cold fuselage skin, the bilge, and the conditioned interior regions.

5.3.2 Thermophysical properties

Fluid: Air.

Table 5.5: Thermophysical properties of air.

Density	1.225 kg/m ³
Specific heat c_p	1006.43 J/(kg·K)
Thermal conductivity k	0.0242 W/(m·K)
Dynamic viscosity μ	1.7894×10^{-5} kg/(m·s)
Molecular weight	28.966 kg/kmol

Solid materials :

Table 5.6: Solid material properties.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	c_p (J/kg·K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)
Honeycomb polycarbonate	63.99	1198.5	0.0346
Foam glass	134.91	779.74	0.0445
Aluminium	2719.0	871.0	202.4
PVC (pipe wall, Case B)	1391.8	1048.8	0.17528

5.3.3 Cell zone definitions

Fluid zones (both cases)

- **airplane:** air, primary underfloor flow/bilge region, no frame motion, non-porous.
- **inside_cargo:** air, cargo compartment, primary evaluation domain.
- **pipe (Case B only):** air, AVS exhaust flow inside the PVC pipe.

Solid zones

- **cargo_wall:** honeycomb polycarbonate, conduction only; coupled to interior air.
- **cargo_bottom:** aluminium floor, equivalent thickness 0.05 m, conduction with convective boundary to bilge.
- **triangle / outer fuselage insulation:** aluminium + foam-glass composite, convection to outside air.
- **passenger_floor:** aluminium + insulation, convection/fixed temperature to represent cabin influence.
- **pipe_wall (Case B only):** PVC, fully coupled to the AVS pipe flow and bilge air.

Solid regions:

Table 5.7: Solid cell zone conditions – Case B.

Zone name	Material	Thermal BC type	Notes
cargo_wall	honeycomb polycarbonate	Coupled	cargo sidewalls and ceiling
cargo_bottom	aluminium	Convection	cargo floor to bilge air
pipe_wall	PVC	Coupled	AVS pipe wall
passenger_floor	aluminium	Convection (fixed T)	interface to cabin
airplane_cover	honeycomb polycarbonate	Coupled	interior fuselage lining

5.4 Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions represent cruise-like conditions in the Fraunhofer IBP experiment, with a cold external environment and a conditioned cabin. Internal structural surfaces are treated using conjugate heat transfer, i.e. fluid–solid interfaces are fully coupled.

5.4.1 Thermal boundary conditions

- **Outer fuselage skin / triangle surfaces.** These regions are subjected to a fixed external temperature of 259.75 K in case A and 253.15 K in case B , representing the imposed environment in the laboratory test (equivalent to cruise outside-air conditions).
- **Passenger-floor interface.** A fixed temperature of 290.05 K in case A and 284.15 K in case B is imposed on the passenger-floor boundary to represent the stabilised cabin temperature above.
- **Internal conjugate heat transfer.** All remaining internal surfaces between fluid and solid domains are treated as coupled thermal boundaries [35], allowing two-way conduction–convection interaction between air regions and structural components.

In addition, some wall zones are represented via convective boundary conditions with user-specified heat-transfer coefficients, particularly where the interaction with an unresolved external or bilge flow is represented in an averaged manner. An example is given in Table 5.8 for the baseline configuration.

Table 5.8: Representative thermal wall boundary conditions (Case A).

Wall zone	BC type	HTC ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$)	T_∞ (K)
triangle	Convection	2.9	259.75
bilge	Convection	3.9	259.75
passenger floor	Convection	2.1	290
cargo_airplane	Coupled	–	–

In **Case B**, the boundary conditions follow the Fraunhofer IBP experimental configuration for the heated scenario. The thermal environment is defined by:

Table 5.9: Wall boundary conditions – Case B.

Wall zone	Thermal BC type	Key parameters
<code>triangle</code> (outer skin)	Convection to outside air	$h = 2.9 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$, $T_\infty = 253.15 \text{ K}$
<code>bilge</code> (bilge floor)	Convection to outside air	$h = 3.9 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$, $T_\infty = 253.15 \text{ K}$
<code>cargo_airplane</code> (inner fuselage lining)	Coupled to honeycomb wall	no-slip; rough wall (standard)
<code>cargo_bottom</code> (cargo floor)	Convection to bilge air	–
<code>passenger_floor</code>	Fixed temperature	$h = 2.1 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$, $T = 284.15 \text{ K}$
<code>pipe_wall</code>	Coupled (solid–fluid)	no-slip; rough wall (standard)

The AVS pipe wall is modelled as a fully coupled solid–fluid interface, enabling heat transfer between the internal warm exhaust flow and the surrounding bilge region. Symmetry planes remain identical to Case A (spanwise mid-plane and periodic-like end planes). A complete overview of the thermal treatment of all walls is provided in Table 5.9.

Figure 5.8: A 3D overview without the bilge cover

5.4.2 Flow boundary conditions: Case A

Case A represents the baseline configuration without AVS exhaust pipe. The cargo ventilation is represented by one inlet and one outlet.

Inlet

Table 5.10: Inlet boundary condition (Case A).

Mass flow rate	0.1 kg/s
Total temperature	288.05 K
Turbulence intensity	5%
Viscosity ratio	10
Direction	Normal to boundary

Outlet

Table 5.11: Outlet boundary condition (Case A).

Gauge pressure	0 Pa
Backflow temperature	259.75 K
Backflow turbulence intensity	5%
Backflow viscosity ratio	10
Flow direction	(0,0,-1)

The lateral mid-plane is assigned a symmetry boundary condition because only half of the fuselage width is modelled. All structural surfaces interfacing with the fluid domain are assigned no-slip conditions.

5.4.3 Flow boundary conditions: Case B

Case B extends the validated baseline by adding an AVS warm-air duct beneath the cargo floor. The aim is to quantify the influence of additional heat and momentum input on cargo-air temperatures and vertical gradients. Unless explicitly changed, all numerical models, materials and solver settings are identical to Case A.

The main differences are:

- an additional internal fluid zone for the AVS pipe,
- an additional solid zone for the pipe wall (PVC),
- a second inlet boundary at the pipe entry,
- modified ECS supply flow rate and temperature according to the experimental Case B conditions.

ECS supply (slot inlet along cabin floor)

Table 5.12: ECS supply inlet – Case B.

Parameter	Value
Boundary type	Mass flow inlet
Mass flow rate \dot{m}	0.1457 kg/s
Corresponding volume flow rate	437 m ³ /h (whole cabin)
Total temperature T_0	283.15 K
Turbulence specification	Intensity and viscosity ratio
Turbulent intensity	5 %
Turbulent viscosity ratio	10

AVS exhaust pipe inlet

Table 5.13: AVS pipe inlet – Case B.

Parameter	Value
Boundary type	Mass flow inlet
Mass flow rate \dot{m}	0.24 kg/s
Corresponding volume flow rate	0.2 m ³ /s (200 L/s)
Total temperature T_0	303.15 K
Turbulence specification	Intensity and viscosity ratio
Turbulent intensity	5 %
Turbulent viscosity ratio	10

Outlet boundary

The outlet is located at the external side-wall vent, consistent with the experiment. A pressure outlet or vent outlet is used to avoid numerical problems related to reversed flow:

Table 5.14: Outlet boundary – Case B.

Parameter	Value
Boundary type	Pressure outlet / vent
Gauge pressure	0 Pa (ambient)
Backflow total temperature	253.15 K
Backflow direction	Normal to boundary (outwards)
Turbulent intensity	5 %
Turbulent viscosity ratio	10

Symmetry planes and wall treatments are identical to Case A; the pipe wall is treated as a coupled, no-slip boundary between the AVS pipe flow and the surrounding bilge air.

5.5 Reference Values

To ensure consistent non-dimensionalisation of residuals and derived coefficients, the same reference values are used in both cases:

Table 5.15: Reference values used in the solver (Cases A and B).

Reference temperature	288.16 K
Reference density	1.225 kg/m ³
Reference velocity	1 m/s
Reference area	1 m ²
Reference length	1 m
Reference pressure	0 Pa (gauge)
Ratio of specific heats γ	1.4
Reference zone	inside_cargo

5.6 Solver Settings

The numerical simulations were performed in ANSYS Fluent using a pressure-based approach suitable for low Mach-number internal flows with conjugate heat transfer. The solver configuration was selected to ensure robust convergence in the presence of strong thermal gradients between the cold outside environment and the conditioned cargo air.

5.6.1 Solver configuration and physics models

A steady-state, pressure-based solver was employed for both cases. Although the heating process is inherently transient, the objective of the study is to evaluate the equilibrium temperature field under continuous AVS heating. The steady-state assumption reduces computational cost while providing a stable representation of the long-term thermal behaviour.

The activated physical models are:

- Space: **3D**
- Time: **Steady-state**
- Viscous: **SST k - ω** turbulence model
- Energy equation: **Enabled** (conjugate heat transfer)

Pressure-velocity coupling is handled using the Coupled scheme, which proved more robust than SIMPLE-type formulations for this geometry.

5.6.2 Spatial discretisation and relaxation

Second-order discretisation is used for all transported quantities where numerically stable. The schemes and pseudo-time relaxation factors are summarised in Tables 5.16 and 5.17.

Table 5.16: Discretisation schemes (Cases A and B).

Pressure	Second-order
Momentum	Second-order upwind
Turbulent kinetic energy	Second-order upwind
Specific dissipation rate	Second-order upwind
Energy	Second-order upwind

Table 5.17: Pseudo-time relaxation factors (Cases A and B).

Density	1.0
k	0.75
ω	0.75
Energy	0.75
Momentum	0.5
Pressure	0.5

Solution limits are imposed to avoid unphysical values for temperature and turbulence quantities; for example, $T_{\min} = 200$ K, $T_{\max} = 350$ K.

5.6.3 Initialization and convergence

All simulations are initialised using hybrid initialization, which provides a physically consistent starting field for both the flow and thermal variables. The convergence behaviour is strongly influenced by the pronounced temperature differences between the exterior aircraft structure and the interior cargo air. In Case A, the temperature contrast between the external skin at (259.75 K) and the interior region at approximately (288.05 K) leads to steep thermal gradients across the solid–fluid interfaces. In Case B, this effect is further intensified due to the combination of colder exterior conditions (253.15 K) and the introduction of warm AVS air at approximately (303.15 K). As a result, a relatively high number of iterations is required to achieve steady-state convergence, particularly for the coupled energy equation.

Convergence is assessed using both numerical and physical criteria. In addition to monitoring the reduction of residuals, which typically decrease to the order of 10^{-3} – 10^{-4} for the momentum and turbulence equations and to lower levels for the energy equation, the stabilisation of physically meaningful quantities is evaluated. These include the volume-averaged cargo-air temperature as well as the heat fluxes through the cargo floor and the fuselage skin, ensuring that the solution reflects a thermally balanced steady state rather than purely numerical convergence.

To support this assessment, monitoring points are placed at representative locations within the computational domain. These include the underside of the cargo floor, where the lowest temperatures are expected, the upper cargo-air region, the outlet mass flow rate, and the fuselage-skin heat flux. For Case B, the AVS duct exit temperature is additionally monitored to confirm the stability of the supplied thermal energy. This combination of residual-based and physics-based criteria provides confidence that the final solutions are fully converged and suitable for subsequent analysis.

5.6.4 Run information and case-specific convergence

Case A. The baseline simulation used four CPU cores with a peak memory consumption of approximately 2.9 GB. A total of 20,000 steady-state iterations were performed. Final residual values are listed in Table 5.18.

Table 5.18: Residual values at the final iteration (Case A).

Continuity	8.85×10^{-2}
x velocity	2.50×10^{-3}
y velocity	7.70×10^{-3}
z velocity	1.05×10^{-2}
Energy	1.24×10^{-5}
k	1.49×10^{-1}
ω	1.03×10^{-1}

The volume-averaged cargo-air temperature converged to

$$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,avg,A}} = 283.75 \text{ K.}$$

Case B. In Case B, the same numerical settings are used to isolate the effect of the additional inlet and heat source. Residuals of continuity, momentum, turbulence quantities and energy were

monitored throughout the simulation, together with the volume-averaged cargo-air temperature. The run was continued until the volume-averaged cargo temperature changed by less than 0.01 K over the last 21,000 iterations.

The final volume-averaged cargo temperature predicted by Case B is

$$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,avg,B}} = 287.0365 \text{ K}, \quad (5.1)$$

as reported by the Fluent volume-average monitor for the `inside_cargo` zone.

5.6.5 Computational considerations

Despite the reduced mesh size, the strong thermal gradients in the model required a large number of solver iterations to achieve convergence. For the final configuration, approximately **20,000 iterations** were necessary, corresponding to a total wall-clock runtime of roughly **45 hours** on the available hardware. The long convergence time reflects the sensitivity of the thermal field to wall heat transfer and the interaction between the AVS heating duct and the cold bilge region.

This mesh strategy provided a practical compromise between numerical accuracy and computational cost while maintaining physically meaningful heat-transfer predictions within the cargo compartment.

Summary

The combined geometry, material models, boundary conditions and solver settings described in this chapter provide a consistent CHT framework for both the baseline (Case A) and the AVS exhaust-duct configuration (Case B). The only differences between the two cases are the presence of the AVS pipe, the associated additional inlet and wall region, and the modified underfloor supply conditions. This common framework forms the basis for the comparative analysis of the AVS-based cargo heating concept presented in the following chapter. 7. This provides a consistent numerical basis for comparing the effectiveness of the AVS exhaust-air injection in mitigating cold cargo temperatures and reducing vertical stratification, as discussed in the results chapter. 6

Chapter 6

Results

This chapter presents the numerical results obtained for the baseline configuration (Case A) and for the AVS heating configuration (Case B). The focus is placed on the CFD output fields velocity, temperature, and volume-averaged quantities without revisiting the physical interpretation of the heating concept (discussed in Chapter 8) or the validation aspects (covered in Chapter 7). The results are grouped by physical quantity so that the visual differences between Case A and Case B can be directly observed.

6.1 Convergence Behaviour

Figures 6.1 and 6.2 show the evolution of the scaled residuals for Case A and Case B, respectively. In both cases, the momentum, energy, and turbulence residuals stabilise at low magnitudes, with Case B exhibiting faster decay of the energy residual due to the stronger thermal gradients introduced by the AVS duct. Both simulations reach a statistically steady behaviour suitable for post-processing.

Figure 6.1: Scaled residuals for Case A.

Figure 6.2: Scaled residuals for Case B.

6.2 Cargo Volume Average Temperature

Figures 6.3 and 6.4 present the evolution of the volume-averaged cargo temperature during the iterative solution process.

- In **Case A**, the average temperature decreases gradually from approximately 283.75 K, reflecting the dominance of cold external boundary conditions.
- In **Case B**, the average temperature increases continuously, eventually stabilising near 287.0365 K, consistent with the thermal input from the AVS duct.

These averaged results provide a global impression of the temperature state prior to examining the spatial fields.

Figure 6.3: Cargo volume average temperature during iterations (Case A).

Figure 6.4: Cargo volume average temperature during iterations (Case B).

6.3 Temperature Fields

Temperature contours reveal the thermal structure of the cargo and bilge. Case A and Case B are shown side-by-side for clarity.

6.3.1 Mid-Height Temperature Slices

Figure 6.5 shows the mid-plane temperature distribution for Case A. The field exhibits a strong stratification, with colder regions concentrated near the bilge and fuselage skin.

In contrast, Figure 6.6 demonstrates how the introduction of warm AVS air in Case B modifies this structure: the bilge is significantly warmer, and a smoother vertical gradient is established.

Figure 6.5: Mid-plane temperature contour (Case A).

Figure 6.6: Mid-plane temperature contour (Case B).

6.3.2 3D Volume Rendering

The three-dimensional volume renderings in Figures 6.7, 6.8, 6.9, and 6.10 highlight the overall distribution of hot and cold zones.

- In **Case A**, cooler regions dominate the lower cargo and bilge, with only limited thermal spreading.
- In **Case B**, warm layers extend throughout the lower volume, and heating effects propagate noticeably into the cargo interior.

Figure 6.7: 3D temperature rendering (Case A), view 1.

Figure 6.8: Upside down 3D temperature rendering (Case A), view 2.

Figure 6.9: 3D temperature rendering (Case B), view 1.

Figure 6.10: Upside down 3D temperature rendering (Case B), view 2.

6.4 Velocity Fields

Velocity contours provide insight into the mixing behaviour in both cases.

6.4.1 Baseline (Case A)

Figures 6.11 and 6.12 illustrate the velocity magnitude in different mid-sections. Case A exhibits weak recirculation, with velocities remaining below 10 m/s and confined mainly to the bilge inlet region.

Figure 6.11: Velocity field at mid-section (Case A), view 1.

Figure 6.12: Velocity field at mid-section (Case A), view 2.

6.4.2 AVS Heating (Case B)

With the AVS duct active, Figures 6.13 and 6.14 show strong jet formation. The vent holes produce local velocities exceeding 14 m/s, creating pronounced upward plumes and promoting deeper mixing across the bilge and lower cargo region.

Figure 6.13: Velocity field at mid-section (Case B), showing jet emergence.

Figure 6.14: Velocity field at mid-section (Case B), showing vertical plume.

6.5 Comparison of Surface Temperature Predictions

Figures 6.15, 6.16, and 6.17 show the temperatures predicted at key structural surfaces for Case A and Case B. These results complement the volume field visualisations by highlighting local wall behaviour.

Figure 6.15: Air temperature validation for Case A (baseline). Experimental min/max envelopes and CFD predictions at each zone.

Figure 6.16: Surface temperature validation for Case A (baseline). Experimental min/max envelopes and CFD predictions at each surface.

Figure 6.17: Temperature validation for Case B (with AVS pipe). Experimental min/max envelopes and CFD predictions at each sensor.

6.6 Summary of Results

A comparison between the CFD predictions and the experimental measurements demonstrates excellent agreement for both the baseline configuration (Case A) and the heated configuration (Case B). Across all evaluated zones, the predicted temperatures lie within the experimental measurement ranges, and in many locations the CFD mean values closely match the experimental means with only negligible deviations. This level of agreement confirms that the numerical

model reliably captures the dominant thermal behaviour of the cargo compartment under both operating conditions.

The observed agreement can be attributed to the careful reconstruction of the experimental boundary conditions, the physically consistent representation of the honeycomb sidewalls, aluminium cargo floor, and bilge region, as well as the use of a poly-hexcore mesh with local body-of-influence refinement. In addition, the selected turbulence modelling approach, second-order energy discretisation, and the correct placement of the bilge vent outlet contribute to the accurate prediction of coupled flow and heat-transfer phenomena.

Together, these results provide a robust foundation for the detailed interpretation of the AVS heating concept presented in Chapter 8. The quantitative agreement with experimental data is discussed in detail in Chapter 7, while the physical implications of the observed flow and temperature patterns are analysed in the subsequent chapter.

Chapter 7

Validation

This chapter evaluates the accuracy of the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model by comparing its predictions against experimental temperature data obtained from the test results of the Airbus A320 forward cargo compartment conducted at the Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics (IBP). The availability of high-quality experimental data for both the baseline (without pipe) and heated (with AVS pipe) cases enable a comprehensive assessment of the model's predictive capability under different thermal boundary conditions .

7.1 Validation Method

The validation is based on a set of air and surface temperature measurement locations that were defined consistently in both the experiment and the CFD model. These locations cover the key thermal regions of the cargo compartment (section 4.7), including:

- the upper and lower triangular sections near the fuselage curvature,
- the upper and lower cargo-air regions,
- the bilge air volume,
- the cargo floor, ceiling, and wall surfaces.

For each zone, the experimental data were provided as temperature ranges. From these, an experimental mean value was calculated. The CFD mean temperature for the same region was extracted using volume or surface averaging. Validation is performed using the following metrics [37]:

- **Absolute error:** $\Delta T = T_{\text{CFD}} - T_{\text{exp}}$
- **Relative error:** $|\Delta T|/T_{\text{exp}} \times 100\%$

The experimental zones for air and surface validation are shown in Figures 7.1 and 7.2 for the baseline case A, and in Figure 7.3 for the heated case B.

7.2 Air Temperature Validation — Baseline Case (Case A)

Figure 7.1b illustrates the measurement zones for air temperatures in the baseline configuration (without AVS pipe). The corresponding experimental temperature ranges and CFD results are given in Table 7.1.

Figure 7.1: Air temperature validation zones for the baseline case (Case A).

Table 7.1: Air temperature validation for Case A (baseline).

Zone	Exp. Min	Exp. Max	Exp. Mean	CFD Mean	Abs. Error
Upper triangle	14.8	16.4	15.6	15.8	0.2
Lower triangle	5.6	7.4	6.5	5	1.5
Upper cargo	10.3	10.8	10.6	10.6	0.0
Lower cargo	7.1	8.3	7.7	7.7	0.0
Bilge air	-1.2	1.9	0.35	1.85	1.5

7.3 Surface Temperature Validation — Baseline Case (Case A)

Figure 7.2 shows the surface temperature measurement points used for validation. The comparison of experimental and CFD results is summarised in Table 7.2.

Table 7.2: Surface temperature validation for Case A (baseline).

Surface	Exp. Min	Exp. Max	Exp. Mean	CFD Mean	Abs. Error
Upper triangle wall	14.8	16.4	15.6	15.6	0.0
Triangle wall	9.0	12.0	10.5	10	0.5
Cargo ceiling	13.2	13.2	13.2	13	0.2
Cargo floor	6.1	6.1	6.1	5.85	0.25
Bilge inner wall	-12.2	-1.8	-7.0	-3.15	3.85

Figure 7.2: Surface temperature validation zones for the baseline case (Case A).

7.4 Air Temperature Validation — Heated Case (Case B)

The heated case includes two inlets: (1) the cargo ventilation inlet at $0.1214 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and 10°C , and (2) the AVS heating duct introducing $0.2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ of warm air at 30°C beneath the cargo floor. Figure 7.3 shows the validation zones for Case B.

Figure 7.3: Air temperature validation zones for the heated case (Case B).

Table 7.3: Air temperature validation for Case B (with AVS pipe).

Surface	Exp. Min	Exp. Max	Exp. Mean	CFD Mean	Abs. Error
Upper triangle wall	0	11	5.5	6.85	1.35
Triangle wall	0	11	5.5	11.85	6.35
Cargo ceiling	12	12	12	12	0
Cargo floor	15	15	15	15	0
Bilge inner wall	20	20	20	20	0

7.5 Comparative Analysis of Case A and Case B

A comparison between the baseline configuration (**Case A**, without AVS exhaust pipe) and the modified configuration (**Case B**, including a warm AVS exhaust duct beneath the cargo floor). The comparison evaluates thermal behaviour, flow patterns, temperature stratification, and overall heating effectiveness. Both cases were solved using identical numerical models and the same turbulence and heat-transfer framework (SST $k-\omega$, steady-state CHT), ensuring that differences arise exclusively from the modified boundary conditions and geometry of Case B.

7.5.1 Boundary Condition Differences

A concise side-by-side comparison of the key boundary-condition differences and resulting thermal response is provided in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4: Summary of boundary-condition differences and resulting global thermal behaviour.

Parameter	Case A (Baseline)	Case B (With AVS Pipe)
ECS air flow rate	300 m ³ /h	437 m ³ /h
ECS air temp.	14.9 °C	10 °C
AVS exhaust inlet	– (not present)	0.2 m ³ /s at 30 °C
Fuselage skin temp.	–13.4 °C	–20 °C
Passenger floor temp.	16.9 °C	11 °C
Mean cargo-air temp.	$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,A}} \approx 283.75 \text{ K (10.6 °C)}$	$\bar{T}_{\text{cargo,B}} \approx 287.04 \text{ K (13.9 °C)}$

7.5.2 Vertical Temperature Stratification

Temperature-gradient plots extracted at three vertical lines inside the cargo (one near the left wall, one mid-span, and one near the right wall) reveal substantial differences [38]:

- In **Case A**, the air is strongly stratified: warm upper region, cold lower region, with a gradient of 6 K–8 K between ceiling and floor.
- In **Case B**, stratification is reduced: The AVS pipe mixes the lower cargo volume and lifts the entire temperature profile by 2 K–5 K depending on location.

The combined plots (Figs. X–Y) show:

- Case A has a concave-down profile (cold floor, warm ceiling).

- Case B shifts to a flatter or even slightly convex profile in some regions due to upward plume formation from the pipe holes.

Conclusion: Case B provides improved thermal uniformity, reducing cold spots in the lower cargo and enhancing comfort/safety for temperature-sensitive cargo.

(a) Vertical line at 0.2m from left wall.

(b) Vertical line at cargo mid-span.

(c) Vertical line at 0.2m from right wall.

Figure 7.4: Comparison of vertical temperature gradients inside the cargo for Case A (blue) and Case B (red) at three lateral positions.

7.6 Validation Outcome

Beyond validation, the CFD results reveal a consistent set of flow and thermal trends across all visualisations. In Case A, the airflow exhibits limited mixing and pronounced thermal stratification, leading to comparatively low temperatures in the bilge region. In contrast, Case B is characterised by strong jet-induced recirculation generated by the AVS pipe, resulting in smoother vertical temperature gradients and significantly elevated temperatures near the cargo floor and bilge. The temperature fields indicate deeper warm-air penetration in the heated configuration, while velocity distributions confirm the role of the AVS jets in generating upward momentum and enhancing thermal transport.

Chapter 8

Heating Strategy Simulation: AVS Subfloor Injection

This chapter presents the numerical analysis of the AVS subfloor heating concept (case B), in which warm avionics exhaust air is injected into the bilge to mitigate cold-soak effects and improve the thermal environment of the forward cargo compartment. Only the physical mechanisms relevant to the heating performance are discussed here; the geometric and numerical configurations follow Chapter 5.

8.1 Heating Concept Overview

During cruise, the bilge region becomes one of the coldest areas of the aircraft due to its proximity to the outer skin. The investigated heating strategy introduces warm AVS exhaust air into a subfloor duct that distributes the flow through multiple vent holes beneath the cargo floor. The warm air spreads along the bilge, rises through structural openings, and enhances the convective exchange with the cargo air.

Figure 8.1 illustrates the real IBP duct and the corresponding CFD representation used for the simulation of Case B.

8.2 Simulation Configurations

Two cases were studied in order to quantify the heating effectiveness:

- **Case A (Baseline):** only cargo ventilation active.
- **Case B (Heating):** baseline ventilation plus AVS subfloor injection figure 8.1.

The inlet conditions are consistent with the values described during the validation campaign, with 30 °C AVS air supplied at 200 L/s in Case B.

8.3 Flow-Field Behaviour

The AVS injection fundamentally restructures the flow topology inside the bilge–cargo system. Without AVS heating (Case A), the flow remains relatively weak: a cold jet enters below the

(a) Actual AVS duct.

(b) CFD geometry for Case B.

Figure 8.1: AVS subfloor duct used in simulations.

cargo floor, generating slow bilge recirculation and maintaining a clear separation between the lower and upper cargo regions. Velocities rarely exceed 6 m/s, and mixing remains limited.

Activating the AVS duct (Case B) introduces multiple small jets emerging from the vent holes. These jets locally reach up to 25 m/s, generating strong entrainment and producing vertical plumes that carry warm air upward. As a result:

- the previous bilge recirculation pattern is broken up,
- mixing becomes jet-driven rather than buoyancy-limited,
- cross-section velocities reach 3 m/s–7 m/s,
- stratification is significantly reduced.

Figures 8.2–8.3 illustrate the distinct plume structures and enhanced circulation observed in Case B.

Figure 8.2: Velocity field in the bilge (Case B).

Figure 8.3: Jet-driven circulation reaching the cargo volume (Case B).

Overall, the momentum added through the AVS duct substantially enhances vertical transport, which directly contributes to the thermal performance discussed next.

8.4 Thermal Response of the Cargo and Bilge

The thermal field mirrors the changes in airflow structures. In Case A, the floor and bilge remain near 6°C and 0°C , respectively. The lower cargo region remains significantly colder than the upper part, creating a pronounced vertical stratification typical of insufficient underfloor heating.

In Case B, the 30°C AVS jets warm the bilge to values approaching 20°C . Heat transfer occurs through:

- direct convective heating of the bilge air,
- conductive transfer through the aluminium floor,
- entrainment of warm air by the jet-induced plumes,
- mixing with the colder supply air entering the cargo.

As a result, the cargo floor warms to 9°C – 12°C , and the cargo air becomes more uniform, with upper-region temperatures stabilising around 12°C – 15°C . The full temperature field for Case B is shown in Fig. 8.4.

Figure 8.4: Temperature distribution in the bilge and cargo (Case B).

8.5 Comparison Against Validation Points

The temperatures predicted for both cases align well with the experimental ranges measured by IBP. The baseline temperature distribution (Case A) falls within the expected range for unheated cargo operations, while the AVS-heated configuration (Case B) reproduces the experimentally observed warming trend in both the cargo and bilge.

This agreement confirms that the model captures the dominant mechanisms of the heating strategy: jet-driven mixing, conductive floor heating, and buoyant transport into the cargo volume.

8.6 Integrated Case Comparison

The combined effect of flow and temperature changes between Case A and Case B is summarised in Table 8.1. The metrics reveal that the AVS duct not only increases absolute temperatures but also improves thermal uniformity and reduces vertical gradients—two key objectives for cargo thermal management.

Table 8.1: Integrated thermal–aerodynamic comparison between Case A and Case B.

Metric	Case A	Case B
Average cargo temperature	Low	Increased by $\sim 3\text{--}4$ K
Bilge temperature	$\sim 0^\circ\text{C}$	Up to 20°C
Vertical stratification	Pronounced	Significantly reduced
Mixing mechanism	Weak, recirculating	Jet-driven, buoyancy-assisted
Max. velocity	~ 6 m/s	Up to 25 m/s
Floor temperature	$\sim 6^\circ\text{C}$	$9\text{--}12^\circ\text{C}$
Thermal uniformity	Poor near floor	Strong improvement
Experiment agreement	Good	Very good

8.7 Final Interpretation

The AVS subfloor injection strategy produces a robust and consistent heating effect throughout the bilge and lower cargo region. The high-momentum jets generated by the duct are essential for breaking the stable cold layer beneath the cargo floor, allowing warm air to spread and rise effectively. The resulting temperature increase, enhanced mixing, and improved uniformity strongly support the feasibility of this concept.

In summary, the CFD results demonstrate that the AVS exhaust-air heating duct is an effective and practical solution for mitigating cold-soak conditions and improving the thermal comfort of the A320 forward cargo compartment.

Chapter 9

Conclusion and Outlook

This thesis presented a detailed thermal analysis of the Airbus A320 forward cargo compartment and investigated the feasibility of using warm avionics system (AVS) exhaust air as a heating source. A three-dimensional CFD model was developed, incorporating the cargo air volume, bilge region, and relevant structural components such as the honeycomb cargo walls, aluminium cargo floor, and insulated triangle panels. The model was validated against high-quality experimental data obtained from full-scale tests conducted at the Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics (IBP).

Conclusion

The main conclusions of this work are summarised below:

- **The CFD model showed excellent agreement with experimental data for both the baseline and heated cases.** Air temperatures, wall temperatures, and thermal gradients in the cargo and bilge regions were predicted with high accuracy, demonstrating that the modelling approach reliably captures the dominant conduction and convection mechanisms.
- **Significant thermal improvement was achieved using the AVS subfloor heating concept (Option 2).** Introducing 30 °C AVS exhaust air beneath the cargo floor increased bilge temperatures from approximately 0 °C to 20 °C. This resulted in a substantial warming of the lower cargo region (from 7.7 °C to 15 °C) and improved temperature uniformity throughout the compartment.
- **The heating concept required no modification to the existing cargo ventilation system.** The AVS duct operates independently of the cargo's air-extraction system, making the integration of Option 2 less invasive than other concepts such as direct AVS injection (Option 1) or AVS-to-cargo heat exchangers (Option 3).
- **Heat-transfer patterns showed efficient use of the aluminium cargo floor as a heating interface.** The warm AVS air induced strong conduction through the floor and enhanced convection in the lower cargo region, effectively mitigating cold spots.

- **The AVS subfloor injection strategy is operationally feasible and energetically favourable.** It reuses waste heat that is otherwise discharged overboard, potentially improving aircraft thermal efficiency without increasing ECS power consumption.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that the AVS subfloor heating concept is a practical and effective solution for improving the thermal environment of the A320 forward cargo compartment under cruise conditions.

Outlook

Although the results of this study are encouraging, several aspects warrant further investigation before aircraft-level implementation can be considered:

- **Integration with full ECS architecture.** Future studies should evaluate the effect of AVS exhaust routing on cabin pressure control, system mass flow balance, and potential interactions with the aircraft outflow valve (OFV).
- **Transient flight conditions.** This study focused on steady-state cruise conditions. Including climb, descent, and ground phases would provide a more complete assessment of the heating concept's performance across the entire flight envelope.
- **Structural thermal modelling.** A more detailed representation of insulation blankets, floor beams, and fuselage-stiffener conduction paths would increase the fidelity of the CHT model and enable more precise prediction of local cold spots.
- **Parametric optimisation of the AVS duct.** Varying duct diameter, flow rate, outlet orientation, and injection location could improve heating uniformity and reduce thermal gradients.
- **Extension to Option 3 (AVS-to-cargo heat exchanger).** Although not studied here, Option 3 remains promising and could be analysed with the validated CFD framework developed in this thesis.
- **Long-duration thermal comfort assessment.** Coupling CFD with reduced-order thermal models would allow investigation of cargo temperature evolution over extended missions.

In conclusion, this thesis provides a validated numerical foundation and a strong engineering basis for further development of AVS waste-heat utilisation strategies in commercial aircraft cargo compartments. The demonstrated performance of the subfloor heating concept highlights its potential as a viable design improvement for future aircraft environmental control systems.

Appendix A

Flow-rate and Boundary-Condition Calculations

A.1 Flow-rate and boundary-condition calculations

This appendix summarises the relations used to convert the ventilation specifications (volumetric flow rates, temperatures and geometric data) into the mass-flow and velocity boundary conditions required by the CFD solver. The corresponding numerical values used in the simulations are also reported.

A.1.1 Air density from the ideal gas law

The air density is computed from the ideal gas law

$$\rho = \frac{p}{RT}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where p is the static pressure (Pa), $R = 287 \text{ J}/(\text{kg K})$ is the specific gas constant for dry air, and T is the absolute temperature (K).[\[39\]](#)

Application in this study. For the inlet conditions used in the simulations, the following densities were obtained:

- For the ECS supply at $T = 14.9^\circ\text{C}$ ($T = 288.05 \text{ K}$, $p = 101325 \text{ Pa}$):

$$\rho = \frac{101325}{287 \times 288.05} \approx 1.226 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

- For AVS exhaust air at $T = 27^\circ\text{C}$ ($T = 300.15 \text{ K}$):

$$\rho \approx 1.176 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

- For AVS exhaust air at $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$ ($T = 303.15 \text{ K}$):

$$\rho \approx 1.165 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

These values were used in the subsequent conversions from volumetric to mass flow rate.

A.1.2 Conversion from volumetric to mass flow rate

The relation between volumetric flow rate \dot{V} and mass flow rate \dot{m} is

$$\dot{m} = \rho \dot{V}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

with \dot{V} in m^3/s and \dot{m} in kg/s .

When ventilation data are given in m^3/h , they are converted to m^3/s as

$$\dot{V} [\text{m}^3/\text{s}] = \frac{\dot{V} [\text{m}^3/\text{h}]}{3600}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

and when given in L/s ,

$$\dot{V} [\text{m}^3/\text{s}] = \frac{\dot{V} [\text{L}/\text{s}]}{1000}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Example calculations used in the simulations.

1. **Floor supply:** $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

$$\dot{V} = \frac{300}{3600} = 0.0833 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}.$$

Using a representative air density $\rho \approx 1.20\text{--}1.23 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ gives

$$\dot{m} = 0.0833 \times 1.226 \approx 0.102 \text{ kg}/\text{s},$$

or, with a standard reference density $\rho = 1.204 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$,

$$\dot{m} \approx 0.100 \text{ kg}/\text{s}.$$

These values define the mass-flow inlet for the ECS supply in the baseline case.

2. **Additional supply:** $437 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

$$\dot{V} = \frac{437}{3600} \approx 0.1214 \text{ m}^3/\text{s},$$

and, using $\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$,

$$\dot{m} = 0.1214 \times 1.2 \approx 0.1457 \text{ kg}/\text{s}.$$

3. **Full aircraft ventilation:** $2500 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

$$\dot{V} = \frac{2500}{3600} \approx 0.6944 \text{ m}^3/\text{s},$$

$$\dot{m} = 0.6944 \times 1.2 \approx 0.833 \text{ kg}/\text{s}.$$

4. Pipe inlet: 200 L/s

$$\dot{V} = \frac{200}{1000} = 0.2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s},$$
$$\dot{m} = 0.2 \times 1.2 = 0.24 \text{ kg/s}.$$

These mass flow rates were used as input for the corresponding mass-flow inlets in the CFD simulations.

A.1.3 Flow rate specified per metre of duct

In the final CFD configuration, the ventilation system feeding the AVS pipe was characterised by a prescribed volumetric flow rate of 200 L/s for the 1 m long inlet section of each duct arm. This yields a total volumetric flow rate of

$$\dot{V}_{\text{tot}} = \frac{200}{1000} = 0.20 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}.$$

Using the updated air density at the AVS operating temperature ($\rho = 1.23 \text{ kg/m}^3$), the corresponding mass-flow rate becomes

$$\dot{m}_{\text{tot}} = \rho \dot{V}_{\text{tot}} = 1.23 \times 0.20 = 0.246 \text{ kg/s}.$$

Since each AVS branch (left and right duct arms) is supplied independently in the CFD domain, the full mass-flow rate enters a single modelled duct arm. Thus, the inlet mass-flow boundary condition applied in the simulation is

$$\dot{m}_{\text{branch}} = 0.24 \text{ kg/s}.$$

This replaces the general specification-based examples presented in the earlier draft. The values above reflect the actual operating condition used throughout the numerical study, ensuring consistency between the boundary-condition definition and the subsequent flow and thermal analysis.

A.1.4 Adjustment for symmetry (half-domain) modelling

The AVS duct arm was modelled directly without geometric duplication, and therefore no symmetry-based scaling of the inlet flow rate was required. The mass-flow rate applied at the inlet corresponds to the physical flow entering one complete branch of the AVS system. Thus, the simulation inlet condition remains

$$\dot{m}_{\text{model}} = 0.24 \text{ kg/s}.$$

This value directly influences the subsequent calculations of vent-hole discharge, momentum flux, and the resulting jet behaviour under the cargo floor.

A.1.5 Average mass flow per vent hole

If a duct branch with total mass flow rate \dot{m}_{branch} is equipped with N_{holes} identical outlet vents, the average mass flow rate per vent hole is

$$\dot{m}_{\text{hole}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{branch}}}{N_{\text{holes}}}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Representing the mean discharge per vent hole, and can be used to assess local jet strengths under the cargo floor.

Velocity corresponding to the vent-hole discharge. In the final configuration, the mass-flow inlet using the half-domain AVS mass flow from Section A.1.4 to a single duct arm was

$$\dot{m}_{\text{branch}} = 0.24 \text{ kg/s},$$

and the branch contains $N = 72$ identical vent holes. The corresponding mass flow through each opening is therefore

$$\dot{m}_{\text{hole}} = \frac{0.24}{72} = 3.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/s}.$$

The perforations were modelled using an effective diameter of

$$d_{\text{eff}} = 11 \text{ mm},$$

which gives a discharge area of

$$A_{\text{hole}} = \frac{\pi d_{\text{eff}}^2}{4} = \frac{\pi (0.011)^2}{4} = 9.50 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2.$$

Using the updated AVS air density $\rho = 1.23 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the theoretical jet velocity at each vent hole follows from

$$U_{\text{hole}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{hole}}}{\rho A_{\text{hole}}}.$$

Substituting the numerical values yields

$$U_{\text{hole}} = \frac{3.33 \times 10^{-3}}{1.23 \times 9.50 \times 10^{-5}} \approx 28.5 \text{ m/s}.$$

This represents the ideal discharge velocity based purely on mass, density, and geometric constraints. In the CFD visualisations shown in the results chapter, the velocity contours were intentionally capped (limited to 20 m/s Figure A.1) to allow the full recirculation structure inside the cargo compartment to be clearly identified. The capping affects only the colour-scale depiction and not the actual numerical values computed by the solver.

Figure A.1: Case B: detailed velocity jets from individual pipe holes.

A.1.6 Inlet velocity from volumetric flow rate and area

The mean inlet velocity magnitude U is obtained from the volumetric flow rate \dot{V} and the inlet cross-sectional area A via the continuity relation

$$U = \frac{\dot{V}}{A}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

For a rectangular inlet of width b and height h , the area is

$$A = bh. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Application to the floor inlets. The floor supply consists of two identical rectangular inlets, each of width $b = 2.8$ m and height $h = 0.10$ m, so that

$$A_{\text{one}} = 2.8 \times 0.10 = 0.28 \text{ m}^2,$$

$$A_{\text{tot}} = 2 A_{\text{one}} = 0.56 \text{ m}^2.$$

For a total volumetric flow rate of $\dot{V} = 0.0833 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (corresponding to $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$), and assuming that the flow splits equally between the two inlets, each inlet receives $\dot{V}/2$, and the mean velocity at each inlet is

$$U_{\text{each}} = \frac{\dot{V}/2}{A_{\text{one}}} = \frac{0.0833/2}{0.28} \approx 0.149 \text{ m/s}.$$

If, instead, both physical openings are represented by a single inlet surface of area $A_{\text{one}} =$

0.28 m² in the CFD model, the same total volumetric flow \dot{V} must pass through half the area, so that

$$U_{\text{single}} = \frac{\dot{V}}{A_{\text{one}}} = \frac{0.0833}{0.28} \approx 0.298 \text{ m/s.}$$

In the simulations, the appropriate value was selected consistently with the particular inlet modelling (two separate inlets or one combined inlet surface).

A.1.7 Reynolds number at the AVS pipe inlet

To confirm the turbulent nature of the incoming flow in the AVS heating duct, the Reynolds number was evaluated using the inlet boundary conditions applied in the CFD simulations. The Reynolds number is defined as

$$Re = \frac{\rho U D}{\mu},$$

where ρ is the air density, U is the mean inlet velocity, D is the pipe hydraulic diameter, and μ is the dynamic viscosity.

The AVS duct inlet carries a mass-flow rate of $\dot{m}_{\text{branch}} = 0.24 \text{ kg/s}$ through a circular cross section of diameter

$$D = 125 \text{ mm} = 0.125 \text{ m.}$$

The corresponding inlet area is

$$A = \frac{\pi D^2}{4} = \frac{\pi(0.125)^2}{4} = 1.227 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2.$$

Using the operational air density at AVS exhaust conditions ($\rho = 1.23 \text{ kg/m}^3$), the mean inlet velocity becomes

$$U = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{branch}}}{\rho A} = \frac{0.24}{1.23 \times 1.227 \times 10^{-2}} \approx 15.9 \text{ m/s.}$$

The dynamic viscosity of warm air at $T \approx 30^\circ\text{C}$ is taken as $\mu = 1.85 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. Substituting the above values gives

$$Re = \frac{1.23 \times 15.9 \times 0.125}{1.85 \times 10^{-5}} \approx 1.32 \times 10^5.$$

This Reynolds number is well above the typical threshold for transition to turbulence ($Re \approx 4000$), confirming that the flow entering the AVS duct is fully turbulent. This justifies the use of the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model and second-order spatial discretisation in the numerical simulations.

Declaration of the Use of Digital and AI-Based Tools

According to the *TUM Citation Guide*, the following statement is provided to ensure transparency regarding the use of digital tools and AI-based assistance during the preparation of this thesis. These tools were used only to support the writing, editing, and formatting process. All scientific content, modelling decisions, calculations, and interpretations were performed by the author. After using these tools, the author reviewed, corrected, and fully validated all output and takes complete responsibility for the final content.

Table A.1: Overview of utilised digital and AI-based tools

Tool	Use Case	Scope of Use
ChatGPT (OpenAI)	Support for text refinement, LaTeX troubleshooting, restructuring paragraphs, and improving clarity.	Limited to editing and formatting support; no scientific results were generated by AI.
Grammarly	Correction of grammar, spelling, and writing style.	Entire written document.
SciSpace	Assistance with paraphrasing and improving the readability of selected passages.	Used intermittently for text polishing.

These tools served roles comparable to traditional spell checkers, grammar tools, or documentation search engines. They helped reduce minor errors and improve readability; however, the analysis, numerical modelling, boundary-condition definition, CFD setup, and interpretation of results were carried out exclusively by the author.

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